

RESEARCH NEEDS ASSESSMENT OF TEACHING AND NON-TEACHING PERSONNEL AS BASIS FOR TRAINING DEVELOPMENT PLAN

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Abstract. This study assesses the research capability of the teaching and non-teaching staff of San Carlos College to equip them with the knowledge and confidence to write research papers. This study looks at the employee's profile, awareness of the research agenda, and benefits of writing research. It further assesses the researcher's primary motivation and knowledge of the research content, resources, research objective formulation, methodology, citation, and publication.

Keywords. Needs Assessment, Research Writing, Training Development Plan

1 Introduction

Research is an essential aspect of academic and professional life. It is a systematic process of collecting, analyzing, and interpreting data to answer a specific question or solve a problem. Research helps us to understand the world around us, identify gaps in knowledge, and develop new ideas and solutions. In the context of teaching and non-teaching personnel, research can help to improve the quality of education and administrative practices.

One of the key reasons why teaching and non-teaching personnel should conduct research is to identify areas for improvement. By conducting research, gaps can be identified in existing knowledge, and develop new ideas and solutions to address these gaps. For example, research can help to identify effective teaching methods and strategies that can improve student learning outcomes. Similarly, research can help to identify effective administrative practices that can improve the efficiency and effectiveness of educational institutions (Sagayno, et. al. 2023).

Another reason why teaching and non-teaching personnel should conduct research is to evaluate the effectiveness of existing practices and policies. By conducting research, current practices and policies are determined if effective and identify areas for improvement. Research can help to evaluate the effectiveness of teaching methods and strategies and identify areas where improvements can be made. Similarly, research can help to evaluate the effectiveness of administrative practices and policies and identify areas where changes can be made to improve efficiency and effectiveness.

Moreover, research provides a basis for decision-making and policy formulation in various fields such as education and administration. By conducting research, teaching, and non-teaching personnel can gather data and information that can inform decision-making and policy formulation. For example, research can inform decisions about which teaching methods and strategies to use to improve student learning outcomes. Similarly, research can inform decisions about which administrative practices and policies to implement to improve the efficiency and effectiveness of educational institutions.

However, writing research is not just a punch to the moon. It requires time and knowledge to be able to at least begin writing the research problem. Equipping oneself with the confidence coming from research knowledge and support, an employee can be able to start writing research. Thus, the need for research needs assessment.

The needs assessment involves the process of personnel evaluation to identify their level of skills and training needs. It is the primary step that should be taken to develop an effective training program (Bleich, 2018). It is an important process that helps businesses determine the context of the training and training period that they need to provide their personnel for them to become confident in writing (Morrison, 2020).

This training needs assessment for research identifies possible training areas based on employee self-evaluation to enable teaching and non-teaching personnel to conduct and write research papers. Knowing the profile, knowledge set, and challenges of the personnel, training can be custom-fit to address impending needs.

2 Research Methodology

This study made use of the descriptive-developmental method of research. It looked into an in-depth assessment of the employee's self-evaluation in the area of research. A Research Proficiency Survey was administered to both teaching and non-teaching staff. There are a total of 44 respondents from different departments such as the basic education, tertiary, and graduate school departments, administration office, registrar, and even the general services. Convenience Sampling was used for the identification of the population of the survey.

The survey comprises of questions dealing with the following:

Table 1. Distribution of questions on areas of concern

Areas of Concern	Question Nos.
Employee's Research Profile	1-4
Awareness of Research Journal, Manual, Agenda, and Benefits	5-8
Research Motivation	9-10
Content and Sources	11-15
Research Objective and Methodology	16-19
Citation	20-22
Presentation, Publication, and Indexing	23-26
Training	27-30

The survey instrument was printed and administered to the respondents. Alongside, an online form of the same survey instrument was created and used to analyze and graph the results by encoding respondent's answers in the online form. Some options in the survey are intended to include wrong answers to determine the knowledge of the respondents, especially on research content and sources. No statistical treatment was used because the answers were interpreted directly from how it was graphed.

3 Presentation, Analysis, and Interpretation of Data

3.1 Employee's Research Profile

On the research profile, most of the respondents have never conducted research in their professional life which has a 60% share (Figure 1). This is more than half of the percentage of the other 4 choices combined. This percentage is followed by 17.5 percent who say that they have been conducting research for at least 2-3 years. This result means that the teaching and non-teaching staff are still very young in the research writing arena and need to be assisted.

Figure. 1. Length of conducting research

The same goes with their description of their experience with research which directly aligns with their length of conducting research. There are 32.5% of the respondents admit that they are a total beginner in the field of research and that they never tried doing so (27.5%) (Figure 2). Although six (6) of them started writing and finished at least 1 research paper, no respondents have published their research paper in national or international journals.

Figure 2. Respondents' research experience

3.2 Awareness of Research Journal, Manual, Agenda, and Benefits

In the knowledge of the San Carlos College Research Journals and the Research Manual, most of the respondents are aware of its existence (67.4% and 51.2%, respectively) (Figures 3 and 4). However, with the close gap between the percentages, there is a need to further inform the employees of its existence and importance because it serves as a goal and guide for the would-be researchers.

Figure 3. Awareness in the San Carlos College Research Journals

Figure 4. Awareness in the San Carlos College Research Manual

Moreover, only a quarter (27.3%) of the respondents know the research agenda of the institution which may be a factor why they are hesitant to conduct research. The same number of people say that they don't know the support and assistance offered by the school for employees conducting research. Ironically, with the employees' knowledge of the Research Manual, they are not aware of the content of the manual.

3.3 Research Motivation

When asked what is their research motivations, the primary answer emerges as looking for or finding solutions to common problems (87.9%). A more tangible answer to the question is that they are motivated to do it because it is a school requirement (42.4%) and a requirement for the job (27.3%) (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Motivations in conducting research

When asked if the respondents were interested in finding answers to questions or topics of their interest, an overwhelming majority of them said Yes (Figure 6). This confirms their enthusiasm to write research and they are in the right purpose in conducting them.

Figure 6. Interest in finding answers to research questions

3.4 Content and Sources

Respondents normally copy phrases, sentences, or paragraphs from the internet, books, or articles but cite them (68.2%) (Figure 7). Although citing the reference is an ethical thing to do, copying is not because it is an act of plagiarism.

Figure 7. Copying from the internet, books, and articles without citing

Although most of the respondents have the idea of plagiarism or plagiarizing content, they still plagiarize. Thus, a need for a system for checking plagiarized content such as using Grammarly, Turnitin, and the like.

Figure. 8. Knowledge of plagiarizing

While plagiarism is common to the respondents, they claim to know how to spot true and fake content. However, when asked where they normally get information and authoritative content, 36% still look at Wikipedia, 19.4% consider tabloids as a good source of information, 47.2% still rely on the content of blogs and vlogs, and 38.9% believe the reliability of magazines (Figure 9). While there is no prejudice on the authority of these 3 sources, most scholars do not use these sources.

Figure. 9. Sources of information

Conveniently, most respondents use search engines the most when looking for related literature in their studies (62.9%) (Figure 10). Although reliable sources of information can be part of the search result, search engine result is based on popularity and not reliability. The media outlets received 14.3% as the least place to search for related literature.

Figure. 10. Place in finding good information

3.5 Research Objective and Methodology

When asked if the respondents knew how to formulate objectives, 71.4% of them answered affirmatively (Figure 11). Additionally, 3 quarters of them know the difference between qualitative and quantitative methods (Figure 12).

Figure 11. Formulating research objectives

Figure 12. Knowledge of qualitative and quantitative methods

Moreover, most respondents know different data instrumentation being surveyed the most identified at 100%, interview with 94.1%, and observation with 79.4% (Figure 13). The least utilized data instrumentation is web search at 35.3% which contradicts the most used way of finding information which is the web search. Either the respondents have little idea that they are using web browsing to find good information or they cannot find good information because they don't know how to harness the features of a search engine.

Figure 13. Data instrumentation used

3.6 Citation

Most respondents know how to cite references (Figure 14). This is a good thing because citing sources of information is an ethical thing. Most of them use APA format which is the most common and popular citation format (Figure 15). They are using mostly Microsoft Word as a citation management app (91.2%) (Figure 16). Although citation management is difficult in Microsoft Word, there is a need to introduce other citation applications for the convenience of the respondents.

Figure. 14. Knowledge in citing references

Figure. 15. Citation format

Figure. 16. Citation tools/software

3.7 Presentation, Publication, and Indexing

While 60.5% of the respondents are willing to present their work or research in a forum within San Carlos College, it is alarming that 39.5% of them are afraid of presenting (Figure 17). This can be attributed to a lack of confidence in the presentation or the content of their research. The Research office aims to a teaching and non-teaching staff develop confidence in presentation and publication. Their willingness to publish their research in the Research Journal also shows 41% hesitation (Figure 18) which confirms the above-mentioned findings. On the other hand, an overwhelming number of respondents (80%) are willing to research if properly guided and motivated (Figure 19).

Figure. 17. Willingness to present research output within San Carlos College

Figure. 18. Willingness to publish research output in the Research Journal

Figure. 19. Willingness to publish research output in the Research Journal

One of the problems in publication is falling victim to predatory journals. The necessity and pressure of publishing research often fall into mischief by biting the offer of predatory journals of fast and absolute non-denial of publication for a fee. When asked if the respondents know what is and are the predatory journals and publishers, 71.1% of them don't know them which is scary and alarming (Figure 20).

Figure. 20. Knowledge of predatory journals and publishers

Respondents were asked if they knew indexing, 28.1% of them said none (Figure 21). Although most of them know Google Scholar as an indexing platform, they are limited on that platform.

Figure. 21. Knowledge of indexing

3.8 Training

Since the respondents are willing to learn, they are asked about the mode of training to be conducted, and an overwhelming majority of them want face-to-face training (Figure 22) in 2 days (65.7%) span (Figure 23) preferably having a quest speaker (75%) (Figure 24).

Figure. 22. Preferred training mode

Figure. 23. Number of days for the training

Figure. 24. Preferred speaker

4 Conclusion and Recommendation

Most of the employees have never conducted research and admit that they are total beginner in the field of research and mostly never tried to write research papers. This statement justifies the need to train the teaching and non-teaching staff of San Carlos College in basic research writing. The respondents also affirm their enthusiasm for research papers with the right purpose in mind.

It is ironic that with the knowledge of the employees in the existence of the research journals and the research manual, they don't know the content of the manual. Thus, they need to present them with the contents thereof. Based on this, there is a need to conduct orientation on the content of the manual and how will they take advantage of what it offers. Additionally, a glimpse of the benefits of being able to publish their research in the institution's research journal should be imparted.

While the respondents know about plagiarism and how to do it, they still do it for the sake of convenience. Some of them still don't know where to find and retrieve reliable and authoritative sources of literature and information. This suggests that there is a need to teach and introduce how to identify and use reliable sources of information. There is also a need to include how to maximize the use of web searching to find good information.

Citing references is a good research culture because it goes away from plagiarizing content and acknowledging where the credit is due. Most of the respondents know how to cite content and use Microsoft Word as a citation manager. Some easier and free citation applications available in the market like Mendeley, and Endnote, among others, need to be taught to make citation easier for the respondents.

There is also a need to orient the respondents on the danger of publishing their research journals in predatory journals and publishers. While this is simple knowledge to possess, research can be thrown to waste if not properly disseminated by trusted journals and publishers.

To further develop the confidence of the respondents in conducting and presenting research output, a presentation workshop should be conducted. A good presentation design, content, and delivery is a must for every researcher because they need to convey their findings to a wide variety of stakeholders. To meet the needs of the respondents and equip them with proper knowledge and skills in research, a 2-day face-to-face workshop seminar (preferably with mentoring) with a guest expert is recommended.

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